

A BRIEF HISTORY OF CHRISTIAN VIEWS ON SEX AND GENDER AND THEIR IMPACT ON EVANGELICAL LEGAL VIEWS

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1. INTRODUCTION: RELIGIOUS VIEWS ON GENDER, SEX AND RACE: HOW COMPARABLE ARE THEY?

U.S. Supreme Court Justice Sonia Sotomayor issued a somewhat surprising stay in a lawsuit against Yeshiva University, an Orthodox Jewish college in New York, which had been ordered by a state court to recognize and support an LGBTQ+ student group on its campus. Justice Sotomayor is known as part of the liberal wing of the Court, which generally is very supportive of LGBTQ+ rights, and her stay was somewhat out of ideological character. Perhaps it was merely a matter of courtesy to the majority of the Court, which is conservative. Indeed several days later, Sotomayor joined her two liberal colleagues, as well as two of the conservatives, Justices Roberts and Kavanaugh, in dissolving the stay.²

Despite dissolving the stay, the high Court made it clear that it did so because there were other emergency avenues that could be pursued at the state level to gain relief from the order. Once these had been pursued, the Court said, and if they were ineffective, “they may return to this Court.”³ It seems that there will be at least the four votes to hear the case on appeal, should Yeshiva lose again below, and that is enough to receive a full review by the Court. While it is hard to determine the motives of Justice Sotomayor in initially granting the stay, it is worth noting that she is one of the six Catholic justices on the Court. Thought she has described herself as being a “lapsed Catholic,” and despite being politically liberal and generally supportive of LGBT rights, Sotomayor must be aware of the position of the church to which she belongs, and the

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²<https://www.reuters.com/legal/us-supreme-courts-sotomayor-lets-yeshiva-university-prohibit-lgbt-student-club-2022-09-09/>; <https://www.jta.org/2022/09/14/ny/supreme-court-returns-yus-case-against-gay-pride-club-to-lower-courts-but-signals-its-interest-in-the-issue?mpweb=1161-48431-19681>.

³ <http://religionclause.blogspot.com/2022/09/supreme-court-vacates-stay-of.html>.

significance of the case for its institutions. She has certainly shown herself sympathetic to the protections of religious institutions in other areas, such as the ministerial exemption. Whatever her long term view of the outcome in the Yeshiva case, even a committed liberal may well pause before doing damage to the religious freedom of institutions to which they identify.⁴

The same is even more true of legal conservatives, of course, who will likely rule in favor of Yeshiva, many Court experts think. But what has made religious conservatives so strong on issues of sexuality and gender? Is this something that could change over time, like issues of race have done in certain religious groups? The Mormons famously switched their doctrinal position on race in 1978 based on new “revelation” from their prophet, allowing black men entry to the priesthood. Other Christian groups have also shifted on positions of race and segregation. Could this serve as a template for a way forward on issues of biological sex and gender? Could traditional religious groups be persuaded, through both carrot and stick social and legal measures, to accept and even embrace modern secular views of sex and gender identity?

The answer is, probably not, because of the very different history, and historical and theological roots of sex and race. Christian dalliance with views of racial hierarchy and biblically-rooted discrimination are relatively recent, emerging in the early modern west with the rise of African slavery. Arguments about the biblical basis of slavery, and the so-called “curse of Ham,” being somehow related to skin color really only became widespread in the United States after the rise of an aggressive Christian abolition movement in the early 1800s. It was only then that “Christian” slaveholders felt compelled to more fully develop biblical arguments and justifications for slavery.

These justifications, while attaining a position of influence in some circles, never defined the views of all or most Christians and Christian churches. They always contended with competing views of humanity and race based on creation of humanity in the image of God; as well as with the gospel message that in Christ, “there is neither Jew nor Greek, there is neither slave nor free, . . .” (Gal. 3:28). In contrast, the history of sex and gender identities and differences in Christian thought, shows a much greater rootedness in theological concepts, and a much greater consistency over time, than that of race. Once this history and theology is understood, it is hard to see how traditional religions, at least those rooted in the Hebrew and Christian Scriptures, could accommodate to modern secular notions of the potential fluidity and subjectivity of modern secular

⁴ <https://www.catholicculture.org/news/headlines/index.cfm?storyid=16760>.

<https://www.brookings.edu/opinions/god-in-government-judge-sotomayors-church-state-record/> (viewed on 9/19/2022).

concepts of sex and gender. What follows is a brief look at this theology and history. It is focused on Christian views and experiences, but much of what I present will also apply to the Jewish and Muslim communities.

2. THE THEOLOGICAL AND HISTORICAL BACKGROUNDS OF TRADITIONAL CHRISTIANS VIEWS OF SEX AND GENDER

The separation of sex (one's biological sexual identity at birth) from gender (the way one presents one's sexual identity) may seem to many to be a modern phenomenon. But the idea of a disconnect between one's biological sex and gender expression has deep roots in the ancient world. The Greco/Roman world was familiar with the idea of men who feminized themselves, and presented themselves as women. Even earlier, the Hebrew Scriptures also contain instructions that reveal the existence of very early pagan practices of people identifying with the opposite gender. An overview of how Christians dealt with this phenomenon in the past can provide insight into how conservative Christians think about modern manifestations of these same issues.

2.1. OLD TESTAMENT BACKGROUNDS: GENDER AND THE IMAGE OF GOD

Christian thought on the topic of sex and gender is guided, even today, by the Biblical teaching that all persons, men and women, are created in the image of God.⁵ The following biblical observations were taken from contemporary reflections on the topic by a variety of evangelical Christian groups. The Bible teaches that the image of God is itself expressed in this sexual dualism. As Genesis 1:27 puts it, “so God created man in His own image, in the image of God created he him; male and female created He them.” The parallelism between “image of God” and “male and female” is unmistakable. Whatever else God's image consists of, it is seen most fully in the diverse identities of the two genders.

Scripture also teaches that God is the author of our sexual identity, asserting in both Old and New Testaments that God “created” all humans “male and female.” (Gn. 1:27; 5:2; Mt. 19:4; Mk. 10:6.) For the Bible, the assumption is that biological sex is the foundation or basis of one's gender identity, whether in appearance, identity, or sexual behavior.

⁵ The discussion of Scriptural backgrounds has drawn from the Biblical Research Institute's Ethics Committee statements on Transgenderism, released in October of 2014, and found at https://www.adventistbiblicalresearch.org/sites/default/files/pdf/BRI_Ethics_Committee_Releases_State_ments_on_Transgenderism.pdf, as well as Don Horrocks, Ed., *Transsexuality: A Report of the Evangelical Alliance Policy Commission* (London, UK: Cox & Wyman, Lmt., 2000), 45-54.

The logic of the biblical connection between biological sex and gender identity is seen in the anthropology of Scripture, how the Bible views the nature of the human person. The Bible teaches that the human being is a psychosomatic unity of mind, body, and spirit (Gen. 2:7; Mk. 12:30). The soul or whole person cannot be reduced to any one of these elements. Rather, the person exists as a holistic expression of the combination of these elements. (Gen. 1:27; 5:1-2; Mark 10:6; Ps. 139:13-14). In light of this holistic view of the human person, it is problematic to hold that sexual or gender identity can be separate from one's body, or that the brain itself can truly be pitted against the body in terms of its sexual identity.

This is not to say that the mind's subjective thought processes might not experience confusion or disjunction regarding sexual identity. Indeed, in a fallen world characterized by physical and mental disease, such confusion is to be expected. The Bible recognizes that the mind and psyche of each person is part of the creation that is corrupted by sin. (Rom. 3:9; 7:17; 8:20-23; Jer. 17:9; Gal. 5:17). As such, the mind and psyche must be renewed and re-created by God. (Rom. 12:2; 2 Cor. 5:17). Human emotions, feelings, and perceptions are not fully reliable indicators of God's designs, ideals, and truth (Prov. 14:12; 16:25). We must have guidance from God, through Scripture and nature, to determine what is in our best interest. (2 Tim. 3:16).

The Scripture reveals this connection between biological sex and gender identity in a number of different instructions. One such injunction is the prohibition against one sex wearing the clothing of the opposite sex. "A woman shall not wear man's clothing, nor shall a man put on a woman's clothing; for whoever does these things is an abomination to the Lord your God." (Dt. 22:5). Another relevant instruction is the prohibition against same-sex sexual behavior, "Thou shalt not lie with mankind, as with womankind: it is abomination." (Lev. 18:22) This instruction against same-sex relations assumes that there is some essential and static quality to sexual identity, or one could subvert the regulation by simply claiming the identity of the opposite sex or gender. The importance of preserving one's biological sex identity can also be seen in the prohibition against mutilation or removal of the genitalia, for those who wish to enter the assembly of the Lord. (Deut. 23:1).

These texts may have had special application, as some argue, in the context of the sacrificial/purity system of ancient Israel. But rather than simply isolated texts that had some unique application in the Jewish cultic framework, these instructions can be seen as consistent manifestations of an underlying biblical commitment to the sacred duality of the sexes. As Dr. Richard Davidson, expert on the Bible and sexuality, asserts regarding the clothing passage, "cross-dressing is morally/culturally repugnant to God not only because of its

association with homosexuality and the fertility cult rituals but also—and primarily—because it mixes/blurs the basic distinctions of gender duality (male and female) set forth in creation.” In a conclusion that applies equally to the passages regarding sexual behavior and genitals, Davidson states that “it may be concluded that the intent was for this legislation to be permanent (transtemporal) and universal (transcultural) in its application.”⁶

Davidson’s conclusion, generally supported by Christian evangelical groups, regarding the universal application of these teachings is supported by the fact that they are repeated in the New Testament. (Rom. 1:26-28; 1 Cor. 6:9) (Christ softens the teaching regarding the eunuch, the significance of which we will discuss below.) These instructions reflect a larger, over-arching biblical theology about the role of gender distinction, and the two sexes, in reflecting the fullness of the image of God in family and society. (Gen. 1:27; 2:21-25.)

2.2. SCRIPTURE, THE GRECO-ROMAN WORLD, AND GENDER

The Scriptural testimony regarding the dual nature of humanity, with both sexes made in the image of God, has stood in contrast to various surrounding cultures. The Greco-Roman world largely embraced a spiritual/material dualism, as articulated by Plato and promoted by various gnostic groups. This dualism tended to view sex and sexual relations as part of the material world, as inferior or even evil. It assigned the male sex to the realm of reason, and the female to the inferior world of passion and emotion.⁷ Aristotle also taught a soul/body versus mind dualism. He believed that women were essentially mutilated men, shown to be such by their weaker reason and stronger passions. Women, eunuchs, and hermaphrodites were “‘lesser men,’ because their inferior bodies were interpreted as evidence of inferior souls.”⁸

Christ’s assertion that “from the beginning” God made humanity “male and female,” and a part of a “good” creation, contradicted both Greek material/spiritual dualism and gender hierarchy. (Mt. 19:4; Mk. 10:6) Further, Christ underscored the importance of all humanity, regardless of sexual function, when he embraced the eunuch—whether “born,” “made,” or “chosen,”—as part of the community of faith. (Mat. 19:12).

Some have viewed Christ’s affirmation of the eunuch as the embracing of a third gender, or as some category beyond, or other, than male or female.⁹ But

⁶ Richard Davidson, *Flame of Yahweh: Sexuality in the Old Testament* (Peabody, MA: Hendrickson Publishers, Inc., 2007), 172.

⁷ Megan K. DeFranza, *Sex Differences in Christian Theology: Male, Female, and Intersex in the Image of God* (Grand Rapids, MI: Eerdmans Publishing, 2015), 108-125.

⁸ *Ibid.*, 117.

⁹ DeFranza, *Sex Differences in Christian Theology*, 102-106.

this proposal is to distort Christ's meaning. The context of the passage is about marriage, and the importance of ongoing faithfulness within it. When the disciples expressed disbelief at this high standard, Christ suggested that marriage is not for all. He then listed the three categories of those that may not marry, including those born without sexual function. (Mt. 19:12)

Gender, however, is much more than sexual function. There is no indication in the Bible that eunuchs were considered without gender. To the contrary, in the story of Philip and the Ethiopian eunuch, the eunuch is explicitly called a "man" (aner), and is referred to by masculine pronouns. ("And they went down both into the water, both Philip and the eunuch; and he baptized *him* [auton].") (Ac. 8:27, 38.)

Thus, accepting the eunuch into the community of faith did not contradict the teaching that men should not assume feminine personas or identities. Paul spoke against the role of "effeminate" (malakoi) men. (1 Cor. 6:9.) The argument that the condition of persistent gender mis-identity or dysphoria is only understood in the modern world is contradicted by evidence from classical history. The Greeks were very aware of men who persistently feminized themselves. Indeed, the word they used to describe this condition—malakoi—is the very word used by Paul in 1st Corinthians.¹⁰

Some point to Paul's statement that "in Christ" there is neither male nor female," as ending gender distinctions in the community of faith. (Gal. 3:28.) But many theologians recognize this passage as a statement of equality related to salvation, and not a doing away of particular gender roles in the home, church, or society. Paul was equally emphatic in other places that such roles continued, and should be respected by Christians. (1 Tim. 2:11-14; 1 Cor. 14:34-36; 1 Cor. 11:7-14.)

2.3. CHRISTIAN HISTORY, GENDER, AND SEXUALITY

As the church developed, it unfortunately was impacted by both the dualism and the male-centered view of the Greco-Roman world. Plato's identification of the material with evil influenced the church to develop a celibate clergy. Aristotle's teaching of women as incomplete men led to a subjugation of women as both social and spiritual beings. The inferiority of both marriage and women was an implicit and explicit feature of the medieval west until the time of the Protestant reformation.¹¹

¹⁰ Gagnon, Robert, "The Scriptural Case for a Male-Female Prerequisite for Sexual Relations: The New Testament Perspective," in *Homosexuality, Marriage, and the Church*, eds., Gane, Roy, Miller, Nicholas, Swanson, Peter (Berrien Springs, MI: Andrews University Press, 2012), 82-85.

¹¹ DeFranza, *Sex Differences in Christian Theology*, 117-125.

In the 16th century, Luther and Calvin restored marriage as a positive good both for the kingdom of God and man, both setting examples by taking wives for themselves. Still, the notion of gender distinctiveness and separation, for purposes of modesty, chastity, and protection of the female, were upheld by Protestant teaching. Of course, notions of gender inferiority did not disappear overnight, and the Protestant world is still wrestling with the question of what it means to be both “equal” and “different.”¹²

The central strands of Protestantism, whether Calvinist, Lutheran, Anglican, or the Anabaptists, generally took the doctrine of total depravity seriously. This meant that all parts of the human were impacted by sin, including physical and mental elements of sexuality and gender. Both Scripture and nature were perceived to teach that deviations from physical gender identity and an appropriate (opposite sex) sexual orientation were results of the fall that needed to be modified, curbed, and resisted.¹³

2.4. MODERN DEVELOPMENTS: CHRISTIANS AND GENDER TODAY

In the post-Freudian, materialist, post-modern, twentieth century, the subjective sense of self and desire moved closer and closer to the center of society’s determination of reality and value. Nature, its design, and its purposes, was largely abandoned as a guide to the normative and the good, at least in public life. Belief in a fallen human nature, which possesses inappropriate desires, also waned.¹⁴

This de-linking of the physical from the normative and moral, and the prioritizing of human desire, has caused many in the secular scientific and medical community to view deviations of sexual orientation and gender identity as minority experiences on a spectrum of normalcy, rather than a deviation into the abnormal. For example, the new phrase for gender confusion, gender dysphoria, implies that identification with the gender of the opposite sex is only a “problem” if it causes distress or suffering.¹⁵

It is viewed by many evangelical scholars and theologians, however, that this change represents much more of an ideological and philosophical shift, rather than the natural progress of scientific discovery. Revisions in philosophy

¹² Witte, John, Jr., “Sex and Marriage in the Protestant Tradition, 1500-1900,” in *The Oxford Handbook of Theology, Sexuality, and Gender*, Thatcher, Adrian, ed. (New York, NY: Oxford University Press, 2015), 304-318.

¹³ See DeFranza, *Sex Differences in Christian Theology*, 125-128.

¹⁴ Witte, “Sex and Marriage,” 318; Daly, T.W., “Gender Dysphoria and the Ethics of Transsexual (i.e., Gender Reassignment) Surgery,” *Ethics and Medicine*, Vol. 32:1 Spring 2016, 41.

¹⁵ Mark Yarhouse, *Understanding Gender Dysphoria: Navigating Transgender Issues in a Changing Culture* (Downers Grove, IL: Intervarsity Press, 2015), 14-15.

and politics related to gender and sexuality, they point out, preceded by many decades these alterations in scientific and medical outlook. The release of sexual desires, behavior, and identity from traditional constraints, whether Scriptural or natural, was part of an explicit political and legal agenda of certain 20th century advocacy groups, especially the American Civil Liberties Union beginning in the 1920s.¹⁶

Christians surveying these developments have argued that allowing a person's subjective sense of gender to override all objective physical evidence is a "surrender to a form of *gnosticism*" and a re-embrace of Greek material/spiritual dualism.¹⁷ In such an environment, Christians must make a special effort to stay true to biblical principles of reality. In applying these principles today, it is generally acknowledged, one needs to distinguish between issues of intersex and transgender. Intersex involves the actual and apparent biological ambiguity in regards to sex.¹⁸ Transgenderism, on the other hand, involves a clear biological sex that is at odds with a person's subjective sense of gender. The vast majority of those termed transgender are not intersex.¹⁹

Given the biological basis of their condition, it would seem that intersex persons need room to work out their biological identity puzzle—involving chromosomes, gonads, other primary as well as secondary sexual characters, as well as self-perceived identity—in consultation with parents, physicians, counselors, and pastors. Once their biological sexual identity is understood, then they should be given the tools to live with a gender consistent with it.

In relation to those struggling with a purely subjective sense of transgender, there must be Christian care, concern, and compassion. Some Christians with a dualistic anthropology, where the spirit/mind of the person is separate or distinct from the body, are showing some willingness to accept and

¹⁶ "Long before they founded the ACLU, [its leaders] and others who shaped the ACLU's first policies on matters related to sexuality participated in the sexual experimentation that characterized Greenwich Village's bohemian culture in the early twentieth century." Leigh Ann Wheeler, *How Sex Became a Civil Liberty* (New York, NY: Oxford University Press, 2013), 12.

¹⁷ *Transsexuality: A Report*, 60-61.

¹⁸ Not long ago an international gathering of gender experts proposed that the term "intersex" be replaced with the phrase "disorders of sex development (DSDs)," as this more accurately describes the condition, and does not imply that there is somehow a third gender between the genders. Peter A. Lee, Christopher P. Houk, S. Faisal Ahmed, Leuan A. Hughes, "Consensus Statement on Management of Intersex Disorders," *Pediatrics*, August 2006, Vol. 118, Iss. 2. The Intersex Society of North America, an advocacy group for intersex persons, has employed the new DSD terminology, as it is consistent with their view that all children should be assigned a male or female gender identity at birth. The Society rejects the idea that intersex is a separate gender category, but believes that non-emergency gender-related surgeries should largely be postponed until developmental conditions can more clearly reveal the underlying gender. <http://www.isna.org/faq/patient-centered> (viewed on 12/1/2016).

¹⁹ Yarhouse, *Understanding Gender Dysphoria*, 16-22.

accommodate the expression of transgender impulses.²⁰ But those Christians with a more holistic anthropology of mind, body, and spirit of gendered persons, it is difficult, if not impossible, to speak of a gender identity that is completely separate or opposite that of the body.²¹

Given our belief in the total impact of sin on the person, mind, body, and spirit, it is unsurprising, it is argued, that there is at times confusion regarding reality. Psychologists know that there are mental states and delusions that cause people to reject the reality of their bodies—such is the case of anorexics, (whose body image is opposite reality) the transabled (those who think they are or should be disabled, sometimes termed Bodily Integrity Identity Disorder), or those suffering from species dysphoria (the belief they are actually an animal).²²

Most experts agree that these conditions are treated best as psychiatric/psychological conditions, where the mind is helped to embrace the reality of the body. The alternative is to damage the body, by allowing for unhealthy thinness, the amputation or destruction of perfectly good body parts, or the artificial reshaping of the body into non-human forms. For many Christians, this would be to participate in the marring of the image of God.

This Christian concern is even more strongly implicated when it comes to that element of humanity, sexual identity, that the Bible teaches has a special connection to the image of God.²³ To vary this image is to ultimately distort the person created by God. As one Christian study team has put it: to recommend gender reassignment surgery as ‘the solution’ may consequently be viewed as unhelpful encouragement to submit to the distorted image of self. It is a solution that allows the deep psychological confusion and hurt suffered by transsexual people to go untreated, thereby increasing the prospect of future emotional damage. Rather than allowing this to occur, the Church should be able to offer fuller hope. A Christian response that emphasizes both psychological and physical wholeness, rather than concentrating exclusively on artificial and cosmetic physical changes in the hope that they will themselves produce the desired psychosomatic unity, more truly reflects a biblical view of holistic health.²⁴

Given a biblical and nature affirming worldview, it would seem that purely subjective notions of transgender fall into the category of psychological confusion, and should be dealt with mentally and psychologically. This conclusion is supported by both historic and recent systematic studies of those who have gone sex-reassignment surgery. An early study carried out in 1979

²⁰ *Ibid.*, 101-124; Looy, Heather, Bouma, Hessel, “The Nature of Gender: Gender Identity in Persons Who are Intersexed or Transgendered,” *Journal of Psychology and Theology*, 2005, Vol. 33, No. 3, 174-176.

²¹ See, BRI Ethics Committee statements on Transgenderism, released in October of 2014.

²² Daly, “Gender Dysphoria,” 41-42.

²³ *Ibid.*, 46-48.

²⁴ *Transsexuality: A Report*, 26-27.

showed that while transsexual surgery patients reported some level of subjective satisfaction and happiness with their change, objective measures of underlying mental health, including depression, anxiety, and basic life-coping were unchanged. The results of this study caused John Hopkins University to discontinue sex-change surgery.²⁵

More recent studies have had mixed results, but none have fundamentally altered the conclusion that sex-change is at best an ambiguous intervention, one that has its own costs and burdens. As some Johns Hopkins researchers recently put it, “the scientific evidence summarized suggests we take a skeptical view toward the claim that sex-reassignment procedures provide the hoped for benefits or resolve the underlying issues that contribute to elevated mental health risks among the transgender population.”²⁶

Ultimately, nature has the last word. No-one can truly change their sex. A complete sex “change” operation consists of destroying usually functioning genitalia and reproductive systems, and replacing them with mere facsimiles and physical representations that can no longer function reproductively. The underlying sex identity of the body does not change, the chromosomes, DNA, and web of other sex-related features are the same. This persistence of underlying sexual identity is evidenced by the body’s constant effort to return to its natural state. Thus, there is a need by “change” patients to receive hormone therapy for the rest of their lives to repulse these bodily efforts. Such life-long drug regimens come with side-effects and health risks of their own, such as thrombosis and cardiac arrest, which requires patients to be continuously monitored and supervised by medical professionals.²⁷

Apart from the health concerns for the individual, there are also very disturbing public policy and public safety implications of allowing persons to decide their genders based entirely on subjective perceptions. Separating unmarried men and women, and boys and girls, when it comes to bathrooms, changing rooms, and housing quarters, protects modesty and sexual purity, values for both church and society.

Just as importantly, and even more basically, it also protects women from male predators, whose greater strength and aggressiveness make women particularly vulnerable if society and its institutions are degenderized. This concern is not based on a belief that transgender persons are somehow more

²⁵ This study and its impact is discussed in Mayer, Lawrence, McHugh, Paul, “Special Report: Sexuality and Gender – Findings from the Biological, Psychological, and Social Sciences,” *The New Atlantis: A Journal of Technology & Society*, Number 50, Fall (2016), 110.

²⁶ *Ibid.*, 112.

²⁷ Weinand, J, Safer, J, “Hormone Therapy in Transgender Adults is Safe with Provider Supervision: A review of hormone therapy sequelae for transgender individuals,” *Journal of Clinical & Translational Endocrinology*, Feb. 2015, 58-59.

violent or predatory than others. Rather, it is the fact that once the rules are changed, it will be next to impossible to police against heterosexual, non-transgender men who merely claim to be transgender, but want to gain access to women's restrooms and changing rooms for their own nefarious purposes. Once gender identity is based purely on a subjective sense of self, authorities must accept one's claim to be the opposite gender at face value, no matter what the appearance.

It is well documented that one of the single best ways of keeping women and girls safe in refugee camps and centers is to provide well-secured, single gender bathrooms.²⁸ That we would consider reversing these common-sense bathroom rules here in America, at a time when sexual assault in public institutions, such as the military, is hitting new highs, is seen by some as a sign of the extreme nature of our modern philosophical confusion.²⁹

CONCLUSION

The Bible is an ancient book, and so it is probably surprising to some that the concerns it outlines regarding sexual difference and the need for safeguarding of the modesty and safety of the sexes are seen by many religious people as speaking so directly to many of our modern problems. But if one believes, as evangelicals and some other traditional religious groups do, that Scripture contains fundamental and even divine insights about the nature of the human, and the origin and importance of gender difference, then such a result is not unexpected. From its earliest chapters, through the experiences of the nation of Israel, and into the teachings of Christ and the New Testament, we see a concern both for the importance of the value and characteristics of both sexes, and a concern that they not be muddled or inappropriately intermixed.

The Christian church has at times not appreciated the equality of the sexes as it ought to have. But until recently it was always clear on the importance of the distinction between the sexes, and the need to safeguard that distinction and to protect the appropriate boundaries between them. The evangelical church appears to be resisting the temptation to over-correct from its failure of providing full equality, thus falling into the ditch of sexual and gender sameness.

²⁸ See Amnesty International Report, viewed on June 5, 2017, at www.amnesty.org/en/latest/news/2016/01/female-refugees-face-physical-assault-exploitation-and-sexual-harassment-on-their-journey-through-europe/.

²⁹ NBC News, "Sexual Assault Reports in U.S. Military Reach Record High: Pentagon," by Reuters, May 1, 2017 (viewed on June 5, 2017 at www.nbcnews.com/news/us-news/amp/sexual-assault-reports-u-s-military-reach-record-high-pentagon-n753566).

They are largely seeing that this would not be a corrective, but a lurch into an opposite problem that will have its own dire consequences.

Thus, we can expect that evangelical Christian groups, as well as other religions with biblically-rooted conceptions of sexuality and gender, will very likely mount vigorous legal defenses of their ability to teach and operate on traditional views of sexuality and gender. The response of Yeshiva University to the recent dissolution of the protective stay was to temporarily ban all student clubs, until it can resolve this issue. This may seem like an extreme response to some, but it is the kind of response that can be anticipated from many religious communities in seeking to protect their fundamental religious beliefs regarding anthropology and sexuality. Some have compared this reaction to the closing of public swimming pools in the south once the federal courts ordered them integrated. But this is to confuse a superficial, localized and transitory—if invidious, destructive, and repugnant—situational bias with a millenias' old religious teaching about human nature, identity and family relations that lies at the core of the world's largest and oldest religions.

Traditional religions have shown themselves to have important theological and historical resources in favor of gender equality, and indeed the history of women's rights in the United States shows both religious impetus and leadership at their roots. But the crude imposition of gender sameness threatens to erase the gains made on the gender equality front, as traditional religious groups perhaps over-react and inappropriately recoil away from more equitable gender practices allowed by their traditions, because of fear of an influx of more extreme positions. Ironically, the betterment of gender equality and fairness in religious groups may be more possible as genuine gender distinctions and distinctiveness are recognized and safeguarded.

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